

CHEMISTRY SCIENCES

PROCUREMENT OF ECO-FRIENDLY BINDERS BASED ON END-OF-LIFE TIRE WASTE

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Abstract

In this work, the main properties of the composition modified with the rubber scrap obtained as a result of the decomposition of the NYB-60/90 branded tire, which was removed from service and turned into waste, were studied. Adding 3-5 parts by mass of polymer waste to bitumen made it possible to increase its viscosity by 2 times and its strength by 4 times.

The obtained results show that the penetration of the prepared sample is 1.4 times higher than the standard, and its elasticity is 4 times higher. Adding polymer waste to 3-5 mass parts of bitumen made it possible to increase its viscosity by 2 times and its strength by 4 times.

As a result of our scientific and research work, a new processing technology for the ecological neutralization of polymer products out of service was developed, polymer scraps of 0.16-0.18 mm size were purchased and NYB-60/90 brand bitumen was modified with this polymer scrap.

Thus, the most critical environmental problem was solved and precious raw materials were obtained

Keywords: Oil-Road-Bitumen (NYB), modification, ecology, polymer-bitumen, used tire, Rub rubber (RR).

I. INTRODUCTION

Recycling end-of-life tires is currently the most urgent problem in the world. Many scientific researches have been devoted to the solution of this problem in recent years[1-6]. However, the results of these studies cannot fully solve this important problem. Although the recycling and modification of rubbers have entered the highest stage of development [7-11]. As the number of used cars increases every year, the amount of tires that

become waste also increases with the same intensity every year.

As polymeric materials do not undergo biological degradation, the specified waste becomes "permanent" waste. [13-16] In modern conditions, the relevance of polymer waste processing is not only related to the environmental problem but also related to the use of these wastes as polymer raw materials and energy resources [17-19]

II. METHODOLOGYOGYA

Figure 1. who recycles old tires

Figure 2. Products obtained as a result of processing

The areas of use of rubber scrub are quite wide. Recently, important scientific research has been carried out in expanding the fields of use of RO [1-8]. After car tires run for 90-110 km, their tread patterns are disintegrated, out of service, and turned into waste. There are various methods of recycling tires that have become waste.

After car tires run for 90-110 km, their tread patterns fall apart, causing the tires to become obsolete and waste. Using the device shown in picture 1 to break up scrap tires and turn them into rubber scraps, we have managed to get the following products from one tire- 1 mm rubber scrap (mainly used in the modification of road bitumen);

- 1-10 mm rubber scrubber (used in the pyrolysis process)
- metalloid (used as metal scrap)
- cord waste (used as raw material in the textile industry)
- 0.06-1.0 mm particles (mainly used to clean oil and oil residues from water bodies in picture 2 by processing scrap tires;

Result and discussion

First, we investigated the areas of use of the rubber dust obtained from old tires, calculated the cost of one ton of rubber scraping, and calculated how much it would cost with the proposed technology. The obtained results are listed in Table 1.

Table 1

The main areas of use of rubber scrub

Material	Particle size, mm	1 ton Price, US dollars	Area of the use of rubber scrub
1	2	3	4
Rub rubber	0,06 -1	147	Rubber compound - waterproofing materials - Roof coverings
Rub rubber	1 – 2	176	Sports fields Playgrounds - road surfaces
Rub rubber	2 – 3	300	In the preparation of some sports products
Rub rubber	3 – 5	350	In the preparation of boxing gloves, In the preparation of parts of medical equipment
Rub rubber	4 – 8	235	Flooring, roofing, and sanitary equipment for livestock farms. Bio-component substances. insulation of gas pipelines (-700). Rubber is used in the production of slates and rubber shoes

We preferred to use the most favorable of the indicated areas of use for the preparation of polymer asphalt concrete by modifying the petroleum bitumens and softening their missing properties.

A general view of the rubber scrubber we use to modify oil-road-bitumen photo 3. is also given

Figure 3. Rubbing rubber

Before preparing the composition based on bitumen-rubber rub, RO and bitumen are heated to 160 °C in separate ovens. The preheated RO was transferred to a mixing vessel while the temperature was maintained at 160 °C. The mineral filler was then slowly added to bituminous RO at the same temperature. The mixer is kept at a constant mixing speed to avoid voids during mixing and to ensure the homogeneity of the mixture. When filler RO is added,

the mixing speed is 480 sec for 30 min. It was mixed continuously and the temperature was also maintained at 160 °C throughout the mixing process After heating the composition to 90° C, we added sulfur. The results were analyzed according to the requirements of ASTM D242 (AASHTO, 2011). The modification was carried out using three brands of bitumen and the results obtained are given in Table 2

Table 2.

The main indicators of different brands of PBE

The name of the accountant	Brand of samples			
	PBØ 40/60	PBØ 60/90	PBØ 90/130	Test method
Depth of penetration of the needle into the sample, 0.1 mm at a temperature of 25°C (100 g, 5 seconds) at a temperature of 0°C, 0.1 mm	39-58 20	86-120 41	90-100 29	DÜIST 11501-78
Extension, cm				
At 25°C	28	46	33	DÜIST
At 0°C	9	12	10	11501-78
Softening temperature, °C	49	52	45	
Elasticity, %	73	79	81	

In this work, since we used only PBE 60/90 brand bitumen, we modified it by adding 2-6 mass parts of rubber scrub, and the obtained result is shown in Table 3.

Table 3

Preparation of a composition based on PBE 60/90 brand bitumen and polymer bitumen using different mass fractions RR physical and mechanical properties of its composition

The name of the accountant	Indicators of PBE 60/90 bitumen	Standard 52056 mainly demand	RR modified polymer-bitumen		
			3 mass parts RR	5 mass parts RR	7 mass parts RR
Depth of penetration of the needle into the sample, 0.1 mm at a temperature of 25°C (100 g, 5 seconds) at a temperature of 0°C, 0.1 mm	45 23	47 25	66 27	79 28	65 26
Extension, cm At 25°C At 0°C	35 4	40 3,5	53 9	46 11	50 13
Softening temperature, °C	52	48	59	77	74
Change in annealing temperature after heating, °C	3	2	2	1	1
Brittleness temperature, °C	-16	-19	-22	-26	-25
Elasticity, % At 25°C at 0°C	60 49	80 70	78 59	86 81	83 74
Ignition temperature, °C	230	300	350	420	399
Adhesion (sticking) to sand or marble	meets demand				
Fire hazard	it is dangerous				
Kinematic viscosity at 135°C Dynamic viscosity at 60°C	- -	434 980	990 1994	1717 3265	1694 3111
Volume change by ASTM D 1754 method, % mass.	after passing the test				
Residual penetration, %	-	81	84	98	93
Softening temperature, °C	40	54	66	78	71
Elongation at 25°C, %	110	49	46	33	31
Kinematic viscosity at 135°C Dynamic viscosity at 60°C	672 604	890 610	998 3029	1287 3649	1340 3370

We used PBE 60/90 bitumen modified with rubber scrub to prepare the polymer asphalt concrete mixture. We carried out the amount of RR in the polymer asphalt concrete mixture according to standard T 9128-84. We confirmed that its main characteristics fully satisfy the

operating conditions by preparing polymer asphalt concrete according to the standard recipe, modified, and used as a binder.

The elastic-viscous-plastic characteristics of polymer asphalt concrete samples at 50°C were determined. The obtained results are given in Table 4.

Table 4

Polymer asphalt prepared using PBE 60/90 bitumen modified with R% indicators of the main characteristics of concrete

The name of the indicators	Unmodified PBE 60/90 bitumen brand bitumen (Prototype)	Polymer-bitumen-based binder (suggested)
The highest plastic viscosity, Pa · sec	39,8	52,9
The lowest plastic viscosity, Pa · sec	10,7	18,9
Dynamic displacement limit, P1<2, Pa	20,1	28,2
Equilibrium fragility modulus Gm, Pa when P < P1<2	231	289
Voltage reaction period q · /Gm · sec	719	1121

The result

The destruction of the rubber coating mainly occurs as a result of high temperatures. As a result, the molecular mass of RO decreases. When studying this in an oxygenated and non-oxygenated environment, the maximum stability of RO is observed in the temperature interval of 180°C. Therefore, we adopted the 180°C to modify road oil bitumen with RO waste.

Since the physical and chemical properties of bitumen are shallow, asphalt-concrete road surfaces soften in high-temperature conditions in the summer months and release toxic chemicals into the atmosphere. In order to prevent all this, we managed to obtain ecologically clean bitumen by modifying road-oil bitumen with rubber scraps obtained from old tires. The results of our scientific and research work have

proven that the eco-friendly bitumen we offer is 4 times more flexible than the bitumen currently produced on an industrial scale, and it is possible to increase its heat resistance up to 110°C, which creates fertile conditions for its application in the industry.

References

1. Amirov F.A. (2018) Theory and Practice of Obtaining Composite Materials Based on Polymer Mixtures (Monograph Premier Publishing. SRO Vienna, Austria 234. P
2. Alizade Aydan. (2022) Skin-40 Rubber with the Participation of Simple and Complex Eternals Purchase of Chemically Resistant Rubbers International Journal of Engineering Technology Research & Management, 6(1), pp. 54-63.
6. Amirov Fariz. Shixaliyev Kerem. (2020) Properties of Linear Low-Density Polyethylene. International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering (IJITEE). 9(9) pp. 348-352
7. Kakhramanly Yu.N., Kakhramanov N.T., Gadzhieva R.Sh. X(2011), International scientific and practical conference Fundamental and applied research, development, and application of high technologies in the industry, St. Petersburg, December 8-10, v.1. p.280-282
8. Kerem Shixaliyev. (2019), Theory and Practice of Obtaining Composite Materials Based on Polymer Blends. Proceedings of The Fourth International Conference of the European Academy of Science Germany, pp. 32-33.
9. D. Saepul Ramdan and A. Priawan, "Penerapan Location Based Service dan QR-Code Dalam Pemetaan Lokasi Berbasis Android," KOPERTIP J. Ilm. Manaj. Inform. dan Komput., vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 15–18, 2018, doi: 10.32485/kopertip.v2i1.31.
11. N. A. M. S. M. Mohamad Ali Murtadho, "Implementasi Quick Response (Qr) Code Pada Aplikasi Validasi Dokumen Menggunakan Perancangan Unified Modelling Language (Uml)," Antivirus J. Ilm. Tek. Inform., vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 42–50
12. Y. Widiatoro, "Implementasi qrcode pada berkas kelulusan mahasiswa berbasis pdf web," Semin. Nas. Ilmu Komput. (SNIK 2015), no. Snik, pp. 15–20, 2015.
13. A. Wijaya and A. Gunawan, "Penggunaan Qr Code Sarana Penyampaian Promosi Dan Informasi Kebun Binatang Berbasis Android," Bianglala Inform., vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 16–21, 2016, doi: 10.31294/bi.v4i1.586.
14. F. U. Faridha, "Perancangan sistem informasi pelayanan pencucian mobil pada orange car wash semarang," Sist. Inf., pp. 1–9, 2015.
15. W. Bangkit and T. A. Setiawan, "Rancang Bangun Aplikasi Scanner Car Location Berbasis Teknologi QR-Code menggunakan Algoritma Dijkstra," pp. 1–5, 2019.
16. I. G. Banjar Jawi, "Pemindaian QR Code Untuk Aplikasi Penampil Informasi Data Koleksi Di Museum Sangiran Sragen Berbasis Android," Emit. J. Tek. Elektro, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 6–8, 2018, doi: 10.23917/emitor.v17i1.5917.
17. L. A. Muharom and M. L. Sholeh, "SMART PRESENSI MENGGUNAKAN QR-Code DENGAN ENKRIPSI VIGENERE CIPHER," Limits J. Math. Its Appl., vol. 13, no. 2, p. 31, 2016, doi: 10.12962/j1829605x.v13i2.1933.
18. K. Petrova, A. Romanello, B. D. Medlin, and S. A. Vannoy, "QR codes advantages and dangers," ICETE 2016 - Proc. 13th Int. Jt. Conf. E-bus. Telecommun., vol. 2, no. January, pp. 112–115, 2016, doi 10.5220/0005993101120115.
19. Albăstroiu and M. Flea, "Enhancing the shopping experience through QR codes: The perspective of the Romanian users," Amphitheatre Econ.2023, vol. 17, no. 39, pp